

Fact-checking 5G Security: Bridging the Gap Between Expectations and Reality

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ABSTRACT 5G cellular systems are currently being deployed worldwide delivering the promised unprecedented levels of throughput and latency to hundreds of millions of users. At such scale and reach, security is crucial. Consequently, the 5G standard includes a new series of features to improve the security of its predecessors (i.e., 3G and 4G). In this work, we evaluate the security of currently deployed 5G commercial networks in Europe and North America. Specifically, by collecting 5G signaling traffic in the wild in several cities in Spain, Germany, France, Canada, and the USA, we i) fact-check which 5G security enhancements are implemented in current deployments, ii) provide a rich overview of the implementation status of each 5G security feature in a selection of 5G commercial networks in Europe and North America and compare it with previous results in China, iii) analyze the implications of optional features not being deployed, and iv) discuss on the still remaining 4G-inherited vulnerabilities. Our findings indicate that the rollout of 5G security features in the analyzed commercial networks is still a work in progress. On the one hand, several networks continue to rely on 4G for their core network operations, which hinders the deployment of new security features (e.g., SUCI) and, on the other hand, fully-fledged 5G deployments lack mandatory security measures such as GUTI reallocation after paging. Moreover, we find that some operators fail to provide proper temporary identifier randomization, in both 4G and 5G networks. Some of the obtained results are aligned with results previously reported from China [1] and keep the European and North American studied networks vulnerable to some 4G attacks, during their migration period from 4G to 5G. Conversely, studied networks deployed in North America exhibit stronger adherence to 5G security standards, with near-complete compliance observed, in contrast to deployments in China and Europe, where comparatively lower compliance levels have been observed.

INDEX TERMS 5G, security, anonymity, privacy, data collection

I. Introduction

The arrival of the fifth generation of mobile networks (5G) is substantially changing the way networks are designed and deployed. From the subscriber's perspective, 5G effectively provides improved performance compared with their predecessors, increasing available bandwidth (e.g., to provide on-demand high-quality video services) and reducing end-to-end latency (e.g., to provide real-time augmented/virtual reality applications). In order to meet the performance requirements of next-generation services, initial deployments have focused on the 5G RAN infrastructure and postponed 5G Core

Network (CN) deployments. In this way, by the end of 2023, there will be around 300 commercial 5G networks deployed worldwide from which only around 15% consist of both 5G RAN and CN, i.e., 5G Standalone (SA) network [2]. This has important implications for user security and privacy, as new security mechanisms require both network elements to be deployed. In addition, the growing prevalence of 5G devices is also expanding the potential user base at risk if 5G networks are not securely configured.

Previous mobile generations, such as 3G/4G, are subject to a number of known attacks, ranging from DoS [3] and imper-

sonation [4] to user de-anonymization and localization [5], [6]. In order to enhance the security of cellular systems, 5G introduces new security enhancements, defined by the 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP), and included in TS 33.501 [7] and TS 33.511 [8]. Despite this, while current real-world 5G deployments follow the same architectural security framework reference, neither all of them implement the same 5G security mechanisms enabled by the new specifications, nor they do it in the same way. This is usually caused by the optionality of some mechanisms and by the operators' inherent constraints (cost, compatibility, or performance) [1].

In this work, we report an experimental security analysis of currently deployed 5G networks, fact-checking security mechanisms compliance, and identifying still existing vulnerabilities in current 5G deployments. For those non-compliant or partially compliant deployments, we identify and provide an in-depth characterization of the attacks they are vulnerable to. This work is an extension of our previous study presented in [9], where we performed a preliminary security study of 5G deployments in a single European country. In the present work, we extend our study by covering additional countries in Europe and North America. Moreover, we provide further insights on 5G security by performing a deeper analysis of the observed results, including new studies of temporary identifiers update compliance and registration rejection causes.

In order to perform such analysis, we collect and study signaling messages between various 5G networks and the User Equipment (UE) through commercial cellular traffic protocol analyzers. We perform this study in 5G networks of different network operators in urban and suburban areas of various cities in Spain, France, Germany, the USA, and Canada. These traces include information about the User Plane (UP) and Control Plane (CP) security activation, the subscriber identifiers exchanged, and the Authentication procedures performed for accessing the network.

Our measurements show that the majority of the observed networks are still exposed to 4G-inherited vulnerabilities such as identity and user data leakage and Denial of Service (DoS) attacks because of the yet general absence of 5G SA network deployments, unlike results previously reported in [1] for Chinese 5G deployments in Beijing. Note that this is as expected due to practical deployment reasons; which is aligned with the roadmap specified by operators towards the adoption path of 5G in Europe and North America. GSMA forecasts a 44% average adoption of 5G within Europe and 63% within North America by 2025 [10]. So the migration path from 4G to 5G is on the works but will take some years still to be completed. It is essential to underscore that 5G is marketed as a more secure network with improved user privacy and anonymity features. Nonetheless, operators frequently neglect to apprise users about the transitional phase, known as 5G Non-Standalone (NSA). During this phase, 5G Core Networks are unavailable, and 5G connectivity relies

on 4G infrastructure. As a result, 5G NSA networks are still susceptible to known 4G security vulnerabilities due to the absence of anticipated security features.

Therefore, the main contributions of this work are:

- i) A comprehensive standard compliance analysis for different 5G networks deployed in Europe and North America. We evaluate the actual security and privacy mechanisms implemented by vendors and operators in a commercial 5G network deployment¹. We have further extended our previous work [9] by increasing the number of analyzed 5G networks in Europe and further expanding to cover North America.
- ii) An in-depth analysis of 5G security. To do so, we expand previous works in three ways: a) we survey the most relevant state-of-the-art works highlighting their key contributions; b) we extend the evaluation to new scenarios such as roaming situations or revealing registration rejection causes; c) we perform an in-depth analysis of temporary identifiers emphasizing on the applied refresh policies and their behaviors.
- iii) A more detailed study of security vulnerabilities found in currently deployed commercial 5G Networks, along with the effective attacks they are vulnerable to. We extend this study with a discussion of lessons learned and implementation strategy recommendations.

In Section II we provide an introduction to 5G and its key processes combined with a detailed study of the present works in the state of the art. Then, Section III provides an exhaustive analysis of the security mechanisms defined in the 5G standard. In Section IV we detail our methodology for data collection and its subsequent analysis and in Section V, we report the results, extensively discussing the capabilities, standard compliance, and vulnerabilities observed in the different 5G networks studied. Finally, Section VI concludes this work.

II. Background

A. 5G Outline

The architecture of 5G cellular networks can be logically separated into three main components, User Equipment (UE), the Radio Access Network (RAN), and the mobile Core Network (CN). The UEs establish a wireless connection with the RAN to be able to reach the CN, which acts as i) an authentication entity, allowing/denying devices to access the network; and ii) acting as an ingress/egress point of the traffic generated from/to the internet.

Within the 5G context, UEs are essentially defined as a combination of two components. First, the Universal Subscriber Identity Module (USIM) card, which is used to store user identification data, such as the public/private keys and the Subscriber Permanent Identifier (SUPI), known as the International Mobile Subscriber Identity (IMSI) in 4G.

¹The network operators considered in this work have a market share of about 99% in the USA, about 78% in Europe and 30% in Canada

Second, the Mobile Equipment (ME) hardware itself, which is uniquely identified by the International Mobile Equipment Identity (IMEI/IMEISV).

The RAN is a network of base stations that provide wireless connectivity to the UEs. Currently, 5G deployments are offered in two different configurations, depending on the CN that is serving the UEs, Non-Standalone (NSA) and Standalone (SA). The former, also named EUTRA NR Dual Connectivity (ENDC), is formed by both 4G and 5G base stations (eNB and gNB respectively) connected to a 4G CN (Evolved Packet Core or EPC). In this operational mode, 4G eNB acts as the master node that is in charge of carrying the user control plane traffic to the 4G CN, and 5G gNBs are configured as secondary nodes only for data plane transmissions. In contrast, in 5G Standalone operational mode the 5G gNB is connected to a 5G CN and acts as a master node for both control and data plane traffic from users. The wireless connection between the UE and RAN has proven to be the most vulnerable interface in cellular networks due to its open nature, making it vulnerable to sniffing, spoofing, and jamming attacks. As such, 5G in its Standalone operational mode introduces new security features with the aim of improving its security and some of its major risks and pitfalls [3], [11]–[13].

In order to support the new 5G requirements, both in terms of performance and security, the 5G CN is redesigned following the Network Function Virtualization (NFV) and Software Defined Networking (SDN) paradigms. As such, 5G evolves from 4G CN static entities into modular and flexible Virtual Network Functions (VNFs) interconnected through a Service Based Architecture (SBA). Some of the most relevant NFs in the context of security are the Authentication Server Function (AUSF) and the Security Anchor Function (SEAF), which are integral parts of authentication and key agreement, the Access and Mobility Management Function (AMF), which is the first point of contact of the UE with the core network, or the Session Management Function (SMF), which is in charge of UE session control. In this work, we focus on the security aspects of the 5G RAN, thus we direct the reader to the 3GPP specification of the 5G CN [14].

B. Critical NR Registration Procedure

The initial connection procedures carry essential information required to establish stable and secure communications through the RAN. These processes are based on the exchange of information between parties: *UE-gNB* for the radio link and *UE-gNB-CN* for a higher-level communication layer. Figure 1 shows the procedures performed to securely attach the UE to the CN. The initial steps before mutual authentication are particularly critical because the information carried can not be protected due to the lack of a security context. As such, these processes must be designed to minimize the leakage of user information, preventing third-party observers from gathering the exchanged information and performing

attacks such as user de-anonymization or localization. It is important to clarify that in 5G NSA (and 4G) this process is called *Attach Procedure* while in 5G SA is the *Registration Procedure* and only the latter will implement the security enhancements mentioned above. For simplicity, we further refer to both as Registration Procedure.

1) Broadcast Channel and Random Access

To effectively establish a connection, the UE must perform a set of interactions with the gNB before starting with the registration procedure itself, the Cell search, and the Random Access Channel (RACH) procedure.

The Cell Search procedure allows the UE to acquire time and frequency synchronization within cells with the goal of retrieving cell parameters and system information from the Master Information Block (MIB) and the System Information Block (SIB). Synchronization is obtained by detecting the Synchronization Signal Block (SSB) and decoding Primary and Secondary Synchronization Signals (PSS and SSS).

Then, the MIB is decoded from the Physical Broadcast Channel (PBCH), also carried by the synchronization block. The MIB contains information to access the network and to further decode broadcast information i.e. System Information Block (SIB). Particularly, the MIB indicates how to blindly decode the Physical Downlink Control Channel (PDCCH) and configure the remaining parameters to find and decode SIB1 in the Physical Downlink Shared Channel (PDSCH) (full procedure defined in 3GPP 38.104 [15]).

The RACH procedure allows the UE to achieve UL synchronization and obtain an identifier for the radio communication.

2) Authentication and Key Agreement

The Authentication and Key Agreement (AKA) protocol ensures authentication and security between mobile devices and network services. It allows mutual authentication between parties (users and network elements) and the establishment of encryption keys to secure communications. This process requires a communication channel to effectively communicate with the corresponding instances located in the CN. First, the Radio Resource Control (RRC) protocol will allow the establishment of an active connection with the gNB for the user to acquire radio resources for communications. RRC connection establishment involves the creation of the Signalling Radio Bearer 1 (SRB1) for the RRC messages exchange. After establishing an RRC connection with the gNB, the UE uses the existing radio connection to communicate with the CN (AMF in 5G, or MME in 4G), using NAS messaging. Specifically, the UE will start a Registration procedure with the CN, which is mandatory to be performed by the UE at boot time (or by setting Airplane mode off), using its user identifier. Once the Registration Procedure succeeds, a context is established for the UE in the CN,

and a default bearer is established between the UE and the Packet Data Network Gateway (PDN GW). This results in the allocation of an available IP address to the UE, enabling IP-based internet services in the 5G device.

3) Security Context Establishment

After the AKA procedure, the 5G CN sends a NAS Security Mode Command (SMC) to the user, which indicates to the user which ciphering and integrity protection schemes (e.g., NIA, NEA) will be used for subsequent NAS signaling messages. The NAS SMC transmitted is already integrity-protected -but not ciphered- to prevent a downgrade of the protection schemes that will be used. After the NAS SMC procedure is complete, NAS signaling is integrity-protected and ciphered. Similarly, to activate protection at RRC level, the 5G gNB initiates the RRC SMC, which is integrity-protected but not ciphered. After RRC SMC procedure is completed, both integrity and confidentiality protections are enabled ([16] (subclause 5.3.4)) and the cryptographic material generated is stored as the security context of the user.

C. Related work

Over the past decade, the research community has devoted significant resources and expertise to the creation of advanced analysis tools tailored for the in-depth examination of 4G and 5G networks. In this relentless pursuit of network optimization and security, innovative solutions have emerged.

Wireless Channel Data Gathering: Since early on in the 4G deployment, researchers tried to find ways to perform data-driven analysis of the cellular network behavior, in order to propose novel network optimization techniques and analyze the security of cellular systems. The authors in LTEye [17] were the first to practically demonstrate that certain LTE broadcast channels are unprotected and can be decoded by a passive sniffer. The authors developed a tool that monitors and decodes the downlink control channel, which carries crucial UE information, such as temporary identifiers and resource scheduling for all active users in a cell. Building upon this groundwork, researchers improved the reliability and speed of LTEye with new approaches for control channel decoding, such as OWL [18]. OWL improved the reliability issues that arose in LTEye's channel decoding process, particularly when dealing with non-ideal channel conditions. This was addressed by maintaining a list of active RNTIs, and obtaining new RNTIs from the random access channel. Other approaches such as MobileInsight [19] extract information from the end devices, directly retrieving information from the communication chipset enabling an in-device analysis of the data. While these tools can access all information exchanged during communication, they exclusively furnish data pertaining to one specific user at a

time.

Security Characterization: Several research studies are actively leveraging open-source tools to conduct security assessments in LTE cellular networks, with the primary goal of identifying and highlighting vulnerabilities within the network infrastructure as well as proposing effective attacks that can be performed over the identified attack surfaces. Hussain et al. [20] disclosed different vulnerabilities within three critical processes of LTE (attach, detach, and paging) by investigating the security and privacy mechanisms implemented. By leveraging symbolic model checkers and cryptographic protocol verifiers the authors effectively find new vulnerabilities within the studied processes and demonstrate their viability in an experimental environment. While prior research primarily concentrated on the lower layers of the LTE protocol stack, Ruppercht et al. [21] conducted a security analysis of the data link layer (Layer 2). In their study, they introduced three novel attacks: identity mapping, traffic fingerprinting, and DNS redirection. These attacks were uncovered by detecting information leaks within the control plane communications. Ruppercht et al. further exploit layer 2 information in IMP4GT [4] to introduce a cross-layer attack that directly affects layer 3 and enables an attacker to impersonate a specific user. More complex attacks have been reported by Ruppercht et al. in [22] where the predictability of keystreams used to protect Voice over LTE (VoLTE) communications allowed an attacker to eavesdrop VoLTE calls.

While new 4G monitoring tools are still being developed [23], [24] to enable security-oriented research works, the arrival of 5G has triggered the design of new monitoring tools adapted to the new and more complex 5G NR specifications, including both open-source tools from the scientific field [25], [26] and proprietary tools such as the ones introduced in [27]–[29].

Such monitoring toolkits have allowed exhaustive 5G network characterization in the wild, such as the one done in [30], [31] where the authors provide an in-depth analysis of 5G networks in terms of performance, power, and QoE, and in [1], [9], [32], where authors performed an exhaustive study in terms of security compliance. Other works such as Ludant et al. in [25], have done deeper security studies with the obtained metrics, identifying severe privacy leaks based on the joint analysis of 5G radio temporary identifiers and traffic patterns. Similarly, Attanasio et al. in [33] demonstrate that user traffic patterns can be inferred based on the specific 5G temporary identifiers allocation process implemented by the operator.

The increasing number of vulnerabilities identified in the different generations of cellular networks requires a classification system where privacy and security-related issues can be easily categorized. Stravos et al. [34] proposed a framework to characterize the efficiency of current cellular generation security aspects, considering well-known adver-

FIGURE 1. 5G NR Initial Registration Procedure and Security Features

serial attacks from previous generations and examine and use them to audit the resiliency of 5G in terms of proposed security tools and mechanisms.

Due to the severity of the identified security and privacy threats, regulatory bodies started to elaborate documentation in order to disseminate essential information about the security concerns. For example, the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) launched the *5G Security Project* whose main goal is to help organization manage 5G-related security risks through the identification of gaps in the 5G cybersecurity standards. More specifically, the National Cybersecurity Center of Excellence (NCCoE) within the NIST is a hub where industry, government and academia work together to address cybersecurity issues through a public-private partnership. Recent works from this working group [35]–[37] emphasize the importance of protecting subscriber identifiers and correctly randomization of temporary identifiers to prevent user tracking and/or impersonation. These works provide a detailed description of the problem, a technical explanation of the 3GPP mechanisms designed to mitigate them along with the configuration guidelines.

Our work extensively studies the security compliance of 5G networks with the standard in different countries in Europe and North America, revealing that such privacy leaks can still happen in most of the analyzed 5G deployments, especially in those that inherit 4G vulnerabilities (e.g., 5G NSA deployments) or may not have fully implemented the 5G security specification.

III. Security in 5G NR

Security in cellular networks has been evolving during the different mobile generations in order to address newly discovered threats and attacks. The advancements introduced by the 5G standard [7] are illustrated in Figure 1. The left portion of the figure displays the messages exchanged during the registration procedure, while the right portion showcases the security enhancements categorized for subsequent discussion. The color code indicates the presence of the highlighted security feature with specific messages within the registration procedure. Additionally, Tables 1 and 2 summarise the different security features defined in [7], specifying in the latter where they are located inside the standard.

A. UE credentials and identifiers

One of the major enhancements introduced in 5G SA networks is the concealment of the SUPI (previously IMSI). In previous generations, subscriber permanent identifiers were sent in clear text and thus, attackers could collect this information (or even request it maliciously) and perform impersonation attacks as described in [4], [5], as well as user localization attacks as described in [38].

In order to defeat these attacks, the 5G standard proposes the concealment of the permanent user identifier (i.e., SUPI) into the Subscription Concealed Identifier (SUCI) by using asymmetric cryptography. In this scheme, the SUPI is encrypted using the Home Network (HN) Public Key, which is stored in the SIM card, as described in [7] (Subclause 6.12). The SUPI must not be transmitted in plaintext over the RAN, with the exception of routing information embedded within it, such as the Mobile Country Code (MCC) and Mobile Network Code (MNC). More precisely, the SUPI should be ciphered using Elliptic Curve Integrated Encryption Scheme ([7], C3)), being mandatory for the UE to support the subscriber privacy requirements to enable this new feature (i.e., USIM card must be able to store the SUCI and Home Network Public Key Identifier ([7], subclause 5.2.5)). Currently, 3GPP defines “Protection Scheme Profiles” depending on the technique used for SUCI computation: i) Protection Scheme Identifier 1 (null-scheme), which does not apply concealment to SUPI; ii) Protection Scheme Identifier 2 and 3 (Profile A and Profile B), which rely on Elliptic Curve Encryption schemes to properly apply concealment to SUPI.

However, there are several situations where this new rule can be broken by the operators. In TS 24.501 [39] subclause 5.3.2, the UE shall use the “null-scheme” (i.e., plain-text SUPI) if i) the Home Network does not have the public key, ii) the Home Network has specifically configured “null-scheme”, or iii) in emergency services. It is yet up to the carriers to configure “null-scheme” and send the SUPI without protection over the air and for this reason, “5G SUCI-Catching” attacks are still possible as reported in [40], allowing an attacker to perform user identification and tracking. It is important to highlight that NSA deployments do not provide this security mechanism because their control plane data still goes through 4G eNBs.

To avoid continuously sharing the subscriber identifier (either SUPI or SUCI) over the wireless link, the Globally Unique Temporary Identity (GUTI) and the Temporary Mobile Subscriber Identity (TMSI) were added in 4G, where their temporary nature was meant to avoid identification and tracking of users. However, their refresh rate was sub-optimal, failing to provide the expected confidentiality and anonymity level to the users. Due to their inherent benefits, 5G networks also include temporary identifiers but impose specific guidelines to refresh them. More precisely, the TS 33.501 (subclause 6.12.3) corresponding to 5G SA, defines three new 5G GUTI refresh policies where the AMF shall renew the temporal identifier and send it to the UE: (1) upon

	4G-AKA Weaknesses	5G-AKA Enhancements
UE Identity	Permanent ID in clear-text No GUTI refresh directives	Protected Permanent ID 5G-GUTI refresh directives
Key Derivation	No Bidding down protection	ABBA parameter
Authentication Vectors Retrieval	HN does not participate into the authentication decision	HN takes the authentication decision

TABLE 1. Enhanced Security Features in 5G-AKA versus 4G-AKA Weaknesses

receiving a *Registration Request* message of type *Initial Registration* or *Mobility Registration Update*, (2) upon receiving a *Registration Request* message of type *Periodic Registration Update*, or (3) upon reception of a *Service Request* message in response to a *Paging* message. Aligned with the absence of permanent subscriber protection, NSA deployments also lack refresh mechanisms due to their dependency on 4G eNBs for the control plane.

B. Enhanced Authentication

The Authentication and Key Agreement protocol is also included in the 5G standard (5G-AKA) to provide mutual authentication between all the components in the communication, i.e., UE, Serving Network (SN), and Home Network, with privacy-preserving policies (i.e., providing user ID confidentiality and protecting from user tracking). Furthermore, 5G AKA allows two end-points to derive a new root key after mutual authentication [41]. The root key is used to derive subsequent keys for different security procedures, such as RRC protection. The derived keys and parameters used during the authentication are stored in a *5G NAS Security Context* which is identified by a Key Set Identifier (ngKSI) as introduced in Section B.

Besides protecting user identifiers as discussed above, 5G-AKA has introduced the ABBA (Anti-Bidding-down Between Architectures) parameter, designed to prevent user equipment (UE) from downgrades to insecure technologies, such as 2G, or using insecure configurations, such as weak or null encryption schemes. In the current specification, defined from 3GPP release 15 to release 17, this parameter has a length of 2 bytes and is set to zero (0x0000), essentially representing a security baseline. As the 5G system evolves and incorporates new security algorithms, UEs can be informed about the complete suite of security capabilities required for network attachment. Table 1 summarizes the 5G-AKA security enhancements along with the new 5G UE identifiers compared with the previous 4G-AKA protocol, which is currently present in 5G NSA deployments.

C. Improved Confidentiality and Integrity

In previous generations, attackers exploited information leaks in pre-authentication messages, such as the Initial NAS message, to target various vulnerabilities e.g. Identity Mapping, as documented in [21]. For that reason, the 5G standard mandates that UEs send the Initial NAS messages (e.g., NAS Registration Request) with only the indispensable

fields (i.e., cleartext Information Elements (IEs)) to proceed with the authentication. However, if the device has a valid security context stored, additional ciphered fields (i.e., non-Cleartext IEs) are added to the initial NAS message to safely transmit sensitive user information. Furthermore, 5G forces mandatory integrity support of the user plane and extends confidentiality and integrity protection to the initial NAS messages.

In 5G NSA (which uses a 4G control plane), the initial NAS message, (e.g., Attach Request and Tracking Area Update Request) is exchanged only with integrity protection once the UE has already established a security context (see [42] subclause 4.4.2). Therefore, an attacker could capture this message and gain substantial information, e.g., the additional algorithms supported by the UE, last visited Tracking Area Identity, and others (Handover support, EPC NAS supported, LTE Positioning Protocol capability support...). Note that these fields are the ones sent under the non-Cleartext IEs in 5G SA.

In order to prevent this, the 5G SA initial NAS Registration Request message adds an extra layer of protection separating the content into two parts to minimize leakage of private information: *Cleartext IE* and *non-Cleartext IE* [7]. As the name suggests, *Cleartext IE* are sent in the clear, and contain the minimum information to allow the UE and the Network to establish a connection. The *non-Cleartext IE* are always sent ciphered. Following we describe how Initial NAS protection is achieved.

When the UE does not have a valid 5G NAS security context, the initial NAS message only contains the *Cleartext IE*. Additionally, in order to protect against an attacker manipulating this first message, the UE sends the same content within NAS *Security Mode Complete* message after authentication. If additional registration information is included, such as additional supported security capabilities or the last visited registered TAI, this is sent within the encrypted NAS SMC message, under the category of *non-Cleartext IEs*. In contrast, when the UE has a valid 5G NAS security context, it will be able to securely send the *non-Cleartext IE* within the Initial NAS message. If the network is not able to decode the *non-Cleartext IEs*, the UE will send them again within the NAS *Security Mode Command Response* immediately after the establishment of the security context. More detailed specifications of this new feature can be found in [39] Subclause 4.4.6.

To enhance the confidentiality and integrity protection of radio communications, 5G UEs shall implement New Radio Encryption Algorithm (NEA) 0, 128-NEA1, and 128-NEA2 for confidentiality protection and Radio Integrity Algorithm (NIA) 0, 128-NIA1 and 128-NIA2 for integrity protection (NEA0 and NIA0 are termed as null-scheme protections, and should be avoided except in rare cases such as emergency connectivity). These algorithms will ensure proper confidentiality/integrity protection of both Control and User Plane messages during the communication when 5G is in standalone operation mode. However, integrity protection mechanisms for the User Plane in NSA operation mode were not included in the standard until recently, in the latest 3GPP Release 17. Additionally, the implementation of the 128-NEA3 and 128-NIA3 is optional [7]. Although the naming convention is different, both confidentiality and integrity algorithms remain the same in terms of implementation as in previous generations (EEA/EIA), but aiming to support increased key length (to 256-bit) in the future.

D. UE Radio Capabilities transfer

Before establishing the connection, the UE needs to inform the gNB about the Radio Access Technology (RAT) that it supports (e.g., supported frequency bands, EN-DC support, etc.). Prior to release 16, the security specifications documents [7] and [43] (from 5G and previous generations) do not provide any guidelines for how this message should be sent in order to protect it. Thus, this information was sent without establishing CP security directives, allowing an adversary to hijack this information and perform bidding down attacks [44]. However, from Release 16, the standard defines that the *RRC UE Capability Information* message is sent after enabling security directives, i.e., once the RRC Security Mode Command (SMC) procedure has been completed as described in [7] (subclause 6.5.3) and [43] (subclause 7.4.5).

IV. 5G Metrics in the Wild

Over-The-Air (OTA) data collection techniques allow for real-time monitoring of wireless communications by capturing data flows of ongoing communication between parties. In this section, we will introduce the methodology and tools used for the data collection phase as well as the key aspects studied during the evaluation of the obtained results.

A. Data Collection Methodology

To characterize 5G commercial deployments we have used two commercial protocol analyzers with several SIM cards from different operators². The commercial protocol analyzers used are the *Keysight NEMO Handy Handheld* [27], which includes a debugging tool used for wireless diagnostics, and *Network Signal Guru (NSG)* [28], which leverages the phone's root capabilities combined with the debug port of *Qualcomm* chipsets to provide extensive information on the 5G NR PHY layer besides RRC and NAS messaging.

²For anonymity reasons, we refer to them as Operator A-E

5G Security Feature	5G Standard Requirement	Reference to Standard
Ciphering Permanent Identifiers	Should	TS 33.501 [7] TS 24.501 [39]
	(1) Shall (2) Should (3) Shall	TS 33.501 [7] TS 24.501 [39]
Temporary Identifiers Refresh	Shall (limited CAP) Shall (cip, int)	TS 33.501 [7] TS 24.301 [42]
	Shall	TS 33.501 [7]
Initial NAS Message	Optional	TS 33.501 [7]
	Optional	TS 24.301 [42]
	Optional	TS 38.331 [16]
Integrity	Mandatory	TS 33.501 [7]
	Mandatory	TS 24.301 [42]
	Optional	TS 38.331 [16]
UE Radio Capabilities	Should	TS 33.501 [7] TS 33.401 [43]

TABLE 2. Standard Requirements, messages triggering the security features and references

Similar measurements may be performed with other proprietary tools such as *Radix Security* [29], *5GTracker* [26], *SigCap*³ or *QXDM*⁴, open source tools such as *free5GRAN* [45] and *5GSniffer* [25], or even forks of well-known open source 5G protocol stack implementations (*srsRAN* [46] or *OAI* [47]) such as the ones presented in [24] and [48]. However, data collection from the wireless link as a third-party observer implies different challenges, mainly related to synchronization and data acquisition, and hence, open-source alternatives can gather very limited information compared with commercial analysis tools.

We have collected control and data plane traffic in five different countries (Spain, France, Germany, Canada and the United States of America) using both the *Keysight Nemo Handy* and the *NSG* because both can collect the data exchange between the device and the network. To homogenize the collection process, the duration of the experiments will be

³<https://appdistribution.firebase.google.com/pub/i/5b022e1d936d1211>

⁴<https://www.qualcomm.com/support/software-tools/tools.qualcomm-extensible-diagnostic-monitor.feb127fd-592d-4c60-acad-c7a0a54a99ea#overview>

Country		Spain			France	USA				China		
Operator		A	B		A	A		B	C	A	B	C
Deployment type: SA vs. NSA		NSA	NSA		NSA	SA	NSA	NSA	NSA	SA	SA	SA
Subscriber Identifiers	Ciphering of Permanent Identifiers											
	GUTI Refresh	After Registration										
		Periodic Registration										
		After Service Request (Paging)										
Authentication Procedure		5G AKA										
Control Plane Data (CP)	Confidentiality	NAS	EEA2	EEA2/1	EEA2/1	EEA2	NEA2	EEA2	EEA2	EEA3		
		RRC	EEA2	EEA2/1	EEA2/1	EEA2	NEA2	EEA1	EEA2	EEA2		
	Integrity	NAS	EIA2	EIA2	EIA2	EIA2	NIA2	EIA2	EIA2	EIA3		
		RRC	EIA2	EIA2	EIA2	EIA2	NIA2	EIA2	EIA2	EIA2		
User Plane Data (UP)	Confidentiality	NEA2	NEA2	NEA2	NEA2	NEA2	NEA2	NEA2	NEA2			
	Integrity					NIA2		NIA2				
Initial NAS message		Protection										
UE Radio Capabilities Transmission after RRC SMC												

■ 5G Compliant | ■ 4G Compliant | ■ No Security

TABLE 3. 5G Security mechanisms availability on current network deployments.

set to one minute, and the following steps will be performed within this time window:

- 1) **Airplane mode ON:** The terminal will always start with airplane mode activated.
- 2) **Start data collection:** Once the airplane mode of the terminal is active, we start the data collection tool at the device.
- 3) **Airplane mode OFF:** Disabling the airplane mode will allow the device to initiate the registration process to establish an active session with the mobile operator.
- 4) **Initial registration:** At this phase, we wait until the registration process is complete.
- 5) **Traffic generation:** This phase consists of the generation of ICMP traffic to check the connectivity status and to monitor changes in the radio configuration.
- 6) **Stop data collection:** Finally, we stop the data logging and the collection tool.

Finally, an effective study of temporary identifiers requires long-lasting experiments to study the behaviour during the registration process and the refresh rates applied to temporary identifiers. For that, we run an additional data collection campaign where we replace the *Traffic Generation* step with *ON-OFF Switch* where airplane mode is activated and deactivated. Our experiments are performed on the aforementioned locations with a minimum duration of 15 minutes up to 10 hours, depending on the network availability.

It is important to highlight the non-intrusive nature of all our experiments, where we only collect data transmitted openly over the air in a *passive* manner, i.e. without interacting with the network or other users and just collecting signalling information while using devices with legitimate access to the network through legally authorized SIM cards. The collected information does not include any type of information from other users operating the same cell.

B. Data Evaluation Methodology

Traces extracted from the communication process contain all the information required for the evaluation of 5G network security features introduced in Section III. We look into the RRC and NAS messages to identify the status of the security enhancements.

Deployment type identification (SA vs. NSA). The first step in the evaluation process is to identify the type of deployment to which the user was connecting to. The incremental approach followed by operators towards the deployment of 5G networks results in two different types of deployments: 5G NSA and 5G SA (see Sec. II). The identification between NSA and SA will be performed by using the IEs carried by the MIB. More specifically, in 5G SA deployments the gNB will include *pdccch-ConfigSIB1*, *ssb-SubcarrierOffset* or *dmrs-TypeA-Position* IEs, which will not be present on the MIB advertised by a 5G NSA deployment.

Subscriber Identifiers. There are two types of UE identifiers used within the authentication process: i) permanent subscriber identifiers, which must be securely transmitted; and ii) temporary subscriber identifiers, which must be periodically updated to avoid their correlation with UEs. The permanent subscriber identifier can be found in the *NAS RegistrationRequest* (within the *5GS Mobile Identity* IE) when the UE starts a registration procedure or in the *NAS IdentityResponse* after receiving a *NAS IdentityRequest* from the network and in there, we assess whether they are correctly protected or not as described in Section A. Then, we focus on measuring the refresh rate of the temporary identifiers (e.g., 5G-GUTI and 5G-TMSI) to see their compliance with the policies introduced in Section A. Their values must be updated after each registration procedure within *NAS Registration Accept* message and after *NAS Service Request* in the subsequent *RRC Connection Request*

message as specified in [7], where a new value for 5G-TMSI shall be assigned by the AMF.

Authentication procedure. The assessment of the authentication procedure will focus on monitoring the presence of the ABBA parameter, as outlined in Section B. This parameter is expected to be found exclusively in the *Authentication Request* message in 5G SA operation mode.

Confidentiality and Integrity. To evaluate confidentiality and integrity, we study the security algorithms used for ciphering and integrity protection for both Control Plane (CP) and User Plane (UP). We assess the protection algorithms used in the CP by monitoring the RRC and NAS *SecurityModeCommand* messages, which instruct the UE with the algorithms to use for ciphering and integrity protection, (see Figure 1). For UP, the security is established with the *RRC Reconfiguration* message, which carries the algorithms used for integrity and confidentiality protection per Data Radio Bearer (DRB). In 5G NSA deployments, integrity and ciphering are established also with a *RRC Reconfiguration*. More precisely, under the “*nr-Radio Bearer Config (PDU)*” IE, ([16] subclause 5.3.5.6).

Initial NAS Protection. As described in Section B, the *Initial NAS Message* should follow strict guidelines to protect the information exchanged. In our analysis, we refer to *Protection* within the initial NAS message security context (Table 3) when they comply with the following: i) if the UE has no NAS security context, the initial NAS message shall only contain *Cleartext IEs* (which include protected subscription identifiers, UE security capabilities, ngKSI, or the indication that the UE is moving from the EPC); and ii) if the UE has a NAS security context, the message exchanged shall contain the information given above in cleartext, and the complete initial NAS message (with the corresponding non-clear text IEs) is ciphered in a NAS container. Moreover, we will evaluate whether the UE transmits the initial NAS message integrity protected when it has a valid security context. This protection feature has been present since 4G, and thus also in 5G NSA and SA.

UE Radio Capabilities Transmission. In response to an RRC *UE Capability Enquiry* issued by the network, the UE answers with the supported capabilities through an *RRC UE Capability Information* message. This message is expected to have confidentiality (mandatory) and integrity (optional) protection (see Table 2) and hence, we assess whether the required confidentiality and integrity mechanisms are applied during the message transmission.

V. 5G Security Evaluation

We analyze the collected traces following the guidelines summarized in Section IV. In this section, we present the results obtained from the different locations for both 5G SA and NSA networks. We summarize our findings in Table 3 and provide more details on the 5G SA Registration in Table 4. Finally, we highlight the identified security vulnerabilities in Table 5 and discuss the related work. The

datasets collected and used for this study will be made publicly available for research purposes upon publication.

A. Security Compliance Analysis

Deployment Type: We start our study by categorizing the different traffic captures from the different countries by deployment type. From our measurements, we find that NSA is still the prevalent deployment type across Europe and North America. However, we find that North America is ahead in the deployment of 5G SA networks, and is being offered extensively by one of the three big operators in the USA and Canada.

Subscriber identifiers: Our results regarding the protection of subscriber identifiers are presented in the “*Subscriber Identifiers*” row in Table 3. Our results are split into two rows for permanent and temporary identifiers:

- i) As described in the standard, UEs should transmit their permanent identifiers only during the initial registration (i.e. no security context stored) or as a response to an *Identity Request* message. Our results show that in NSA connections, UEs transmit directly the IMSI in clear text during the initial registration, as they still rely on 4G for the CP. However, in 5G SA networks, we observe that Operator A from the USA effectively transmits the encrypted IMSI (SUCI) using the protection profile B (see Section A).
- ii) Temporary Subscriber Identifier: When the UE has a stored security context, it shall use its temporary identifier to perform the registration. We verify that 5G NSA and SA networks effectively transmit the GUTI when a security context is stored. Moreover, we find that, when a user transitions from 4G to 5G SA, it uses the 4G temporary identifier as its identity during the 5G Registration Request message. Another crucial aspect that we evaluate is the refresh rate of temporary identifiers. In 5G, temporary identifiers are mandatory to be refreshed after i) a *Registration Request* message, ii) periodically, and iii) after a *Service Request/Periodic Registration* message only in SA mode, while NSA mode does not provide mandatory guidelines for temporary identifiers relocation. The “*GUTI Refresh*” row in Table 3 shows our observed results. The GUTI is always refreshed after a *Registration Request* message for both NSA and SA deployments. In contrast, none of our traces show any Periodic or After-Service Request update of the temporary identifiers, showing a complete absence of any *Registration Periodic Update* nor an *RRC Connection Request* (after a NAS Service Request) with a new GUTI value to be allocated. Given that a number of traces elapsed for about 10 hours, the lack of updates in temporary identifiers raises significant concerns about the implementation of this security policy. This is illustrated in the red “After Service Request” row of Table 3.

Authentication Procedure: We observed the presence of the ABBA parameter in Operator A from the USA and Operator A in Canada, where the deployments are operating in SA mode (*Authentication Procedure* row in Table 3). The parameter can be found within the NAS *Authentication Request* message, being then compliant with the standard. Within the ABBA field, we successfully determined the ABBA length, consistently set to 2 bytes in both operators.

Confidentiality and Integrity: A summary of the algorithms used for confidentiality and integrity in both Control and User Plane is presented in Table 3 (Control Plane Data and User Plane Data rows). For the case of 5G NSA, we found that all the carriers protect the Control Plane using both integrity and ciphering (4G) algorithms. EEA2 is the most used followed by EEA1 (EEA3 was only used once for NAS ciphering by Operator C from USA) for confidentiality protection. For integrity protection, most of the 5G NSA traces used EIA2 (except one trace with EIA3 from the previous Operator C from the USA). On the other hand, in all the 5G NSA traces, the User Plane data is always ciphered with the NEA2 5G algorithm, while the integrity protection, a new Release 17 feature, is only present in one trace that uses the NIA2 5G algorithm (in this case, Operator B from USA).

For the case of 5G SA, Table 3 shows that only Operator A from the USA is compliant with 5G security. The SA deployment has enabled the use of new integrity and confidentiality algorithms in the control plane, such as NEA2 for confidentiality and NIA 2 for integrity. It is important to mention that 5G SA has been envisioned to support 256-bit keys to enhance integrity and ciphering mechanisms. However, the 5G SA traces of Operator A show that all the algorithms implemented use 128-bit keys. However, the UE capabilities that were exchanged with the base stations during the *NAS Registration Request* reveal the absence of 256-bit key support from the UE side, impeding the network from using this type of algorithm.

Initial NAS message: As introduced in Section B and Section B, 5G SA introduces guidelines to protect specific information exchanged through the *Initial NAS* message by applying both ciphering and integrity protection. The results of this analysis are depicted in Table 3 at the *Initial NAS message* row where “Protection” refers to the combination of ciphering and integrity to protect the *Initial NAS message* from data leakages.

On the one hand, the *Attach Request* messages on 5G NSA traces show that only integrity protection is present in the transported IEs. On the other hand, 5G SA traces confirmed the presence of two types of IEs in the traces (*Cleartext IEs* to store essential information for the attach process, and *non-Cleartext IE*, which stores sensitive information that must be ciphered before being exchanged) as specified in the standard. This initial NAS message “Protection”, however, was only observed in Operator A from the USA.

UE Radio Capabilities: We have identified within our traces that two operators using NSA deployments (Operator B from Spain and Operator B from the USA in Table 3) are not fulfilling the security requirements for the transmission of UE Radio Capabilities. In both traces the message *RRC UE Capability Information* has been sent before RRC SMC, not having a security context to secure the information beforehand. All other operators send the *UE Radio Capabilities* after RRC SMC and hence, they are integrity-protected and ciphered (see Section D). The last row of Table 3 confirms the compliance with 5G SA (green part) and NSA (yellow part) standards.

B. Extensive Analysis of Temporary Identifiers

The implementation of effective randomization strategies for temporary identifiers plays a pivotal role in safeguarding users’ privacy and preventing unauthorized user tracking as introduced in Section A. Then, during the analysis of the experiments performed in Section A, we saw some initial indicators that seemed to hint that temporary identifiers are correlated over time. To evaluate our hypothesis, we conducted additional dedicated experiments to evaluate the behavior of the temporary identifiers over time. We define a set of experiments aiming to disclose any time correlation of the identifiers to appear by performing multiple registration attempts in different time intervals: “Rapid”, where registration requests are performed every 5 seconds, and “Medium”, where registration requests happen every 5 minutes. Then, we studied: i) the values of temporary identifiers gathered during the experiments; and ii) correlation analysis to identify possible trends in the values assigned to the identifiers.

Figure 2 illustrates the progression of the TMSI throughout the experiments. Each column corresponds to the outcomes associated with a specific operator while rows represent the different rates previously defined. The Y axis represents the TMSI value, which was converted from hexadecimal to decimal, and the X axis depicts the timestamp.

Our findings reveal a correlation between time and the values assigned to temporary identifiers for Operators A and C in Spain, as well as Operator A in the USA. While Operator B in Spain does exhibit a subtle trend, it is not as obvious as the patterns observed in the other operators.

More precisely, Operator A from Spain (operating in NSA mode) shows a discernible linear rise in the TMSI over time for the *MEDIUM* rate. With the *RAPID* rate, the values occasionally remain stable, but still exhibit an increase at certain points in time. Likewise, Operator A in the USA (operating in SA mode) displays a comparable pattern for both rates, indicating a potential time correlation in temporary identifiers in such deployment scenarios as well. On the other hand, Operator C in Spain demonstrates a subtle trend, implying a possible time correlation.

The outcomes from Operator B in Spain appeared to lack an evident time-dependent pattern. However, upon dividing the 32 bits of the TMSI into smaller chunks, potential time

FIGURE 2. Evolution of the TMSI over time for different operators using different operation modes, NSA in the Spanish sites and SA in the USA.

correlations emerged that may have been obscured when examining the complete value. Consequently, we divided the TMSI value by Byte, revealing a possible time correlation in the third byte, as depicted in the small figures for Operator B (ES) (Figure 2).

The identification of time correlations in temporary identifiers could bring to light underlying issues related to the randomization of these identifiers. Even a subtle temporal correlation has the potential to contribute to user tracking.

To further understand the behavior of temporary identifiers randomization, we do an additional measurement where the UE transitions between 5G NSA and SA and across different *Tracking Areas*. Figure 3 shows the evolution of the TMSI together with the operation mode of the infrastructure at which the UE is registered during the experiment. The depicted values unveil certain parts of the identifier to be static while others seemed to present a correlation with time. This behavior is confirmed after a tracking area update because the identifier is drastically updated after this message probably because of the absence of time synchronization between tracking areas.

C. 5G SA Special Scenarios

During our data collection campaign, we identified different situations in which our devices did not successfully perform a connection with 5G SA deployments. These issues can be attributed to operator-imposed limitations such as restrictions on availability (premium users only) or deployments in a transitional (incomplete) phase. However, although the initial registration procedure was partially completed, we could analyze both the generated messages and the replies obtained from the network aiming to study their compliance level with 5G SA standards. The obtained results are summarized in Table 4.

The resulting table depicts in the first row the location at which the traces were collected together with the operator (country-operator pair). Then, given the impact of having

a security context from a previous connection stored in the network or not (see *Initial NAS Protection* at Section IV), we identify the previous state of each connection (i.e., *Previous Connection* row), assuming it is the initial state of each registration process. Finally, the *NAS Key Identifier* row indicates whether the previous connection established a NAS security context that may be used for future connection attempts.

Once the initial state of each connection was identified, we proceeded with the security analysis following the same approach as in previous sections. For a better understanding of the information displayed in the table, the first two columns are taken from a successful 5G SA registration (both correspond to USA Operator A SA in Table 3). On the one hand, the first column shows a UE with a previous 4G connection (terminated with a *RRC Release* message). Despite not having a Security Context (no NAS Key identifier), the network can identify the user employing the 5G-GUTI which is the same TMSI value as in the previous 4G connection. On the other hand, due to the lack of security context in the UE, the Initial NAS message only contains the “*cleartext IEs*”. We have observed that after Authentication (which establishes the Security Context agreement for both parties), the UE sent the whole Initial NAS message i.e., “*cleartext IEs*” and “*non-cleartext IEs*” within the NAS SMC response, protecting this message in compliance with the standard.

In the second column, we present a trace involving the same Operator A (USA), featuring an “Initial Registration” as the Registration type. In this scenario, the User Equipment (UE) possessed a valid security context and a stored 5G-GUTI from a previous 5G SA connection that concluded with an *RRC Release* message. However, the new AMF lacks this information, asking the UE to initiate a complete registration process using its permanent identifier adequately protected (SUCI). It is noteworthy that in this case, the UE sent again the full content of the Initial NAS message

Country	USA				Canada	Germany	Spain	
Operator	A	A	D	E	A	A	C	
Previous Connection	4G	5G	—	4G	4G	—	—	
NAS Key Identifier	No Key(7)	Key (1)	No Key(7)					
Registration	Registration Request	GUTI	GUTI	IMSI	IMSI	GUTI	IMSI	GUTI
	Initial NAS Protected	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	No	No
	Identity Response	—	SUCI	—	—	SUCI	—	—
	Authentication	OK	OK	—	—	OK	—	—
	NAS SMC	OK	OK	—	—	OK	—	—
Rejection Cause	OK	OK	27	—	27	27	9	

■	5G Compliant	■	Previous Security Context	■	No Security
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TABLE 4. 5G SA Registration Reject results

within the NAS SMC response. Looking at the Registration Request row of Table 4, there are several operators from North America and Europe using a permanent identifier (i.e., IMSI) without any protection, as well as sending the *Initial NAS Message* only integrity protected, which differs from the expected security in 5G (integrity and ciphering).

Additionally, we have included the different reject causes identified in the traces in order to provide a better understanding of the overall registration process. The generic rejection cause is a *REGISTRATION REJECT: NI mode not allowed (#27)*, which essentially denies the UE to access the 5G CN (via the NAS tunnel from UE to AMF). Alternatively, we discovered that the #27 rejection cause was used as well by operators to refuse 5G SA connectivity to SIM cards with limited services (i.e., pre-paid SIM cards). Finally, we have captured an uncommon rejection (#9) *REGISTRATION REJECT: UE identity cannot be derived by the network*. In response to a *Registration Request* of type "Mobility Registration Updating", the network was not able to derive the UE's identity from the 5G-GUTI/TMSI because of no matching identity/context in the network was found, failing to validate its identity due to an integrity check failure of the received message [39].

FIGURE 3. TMSI Value evolution across different technology and Tracking Areas (USA Operator A)

The observed patterns in the temporary identifiers suggest a potential correlation with the counters utilized on each AMF/MME for computing these identifiers. Furthermore, there appears to be a static component in the identifier, raising the prospect of user traceability.

D. Effective Attacks on current 5G Deployments

Subscriber technology downgrade (Bidding down attacks): The presence of the ABBA parameter is negligible in almost all the studied networks except for Operator A from USA and Canada, allowing an attacker to easily place a rogue base station to impersonate the legitimate one. This situation can scale from the leakage of subscriber identifiers to the complete UE hijacking [49]–[51].

Subscriber credentials (identity attacks): Since the majority of the studied networks did not implement concealment of the permanent identifiers, the legacy catching attacks can still be deployed [52], as well as more sophisticated attacks that exploit subscriber credentials *leakability* [40], [53].

Our analysis shows that temporary identifiers are only being updated after every *Registration Procedure* is performed, but no other refresh mechanisms introduced in 5G are in place. Moreover, our results on temporary identifier reallocation reveal that weak randomization techniques are currently being used by operators. The lack of frequent identifier refreshes, and the use of predictable reallocation techniques, enables identity mapping and tracking attacks by correlating temporary identifiers with UEs [51], [54], [55].

Authentication vulnerabilities (activity monitoring): Given that the majority of the deployments are NSA, the presence of users and their activity consumption patterns, such as the number of calls or SMS transmitted, can be inferred since they still rely on 4G AKA protocols [56]. Additionally, the authors in [56] propose novel privacy attacks against all variants of AKA protocol which, in turn, affect different scenarios studied. It is important to notice that 5G SA does not implement new security features within the new 5G-AKA to prevent or mitigate the aforementioned attacks and thus, the 5G SA deployments identified are still vulnerable to them.

UP Confidentiality and Integrity: As highlighted in Section A, confidentiality protection is enabled in most of the deployments while integrity protection in the UP, optional in SA and introduced recently in Release 17 for NSA networks, is only being used by one operator in SA mode and one

Security Field	5G NSA Vulnerability	Threats and Attacks	5G SA Enhancement
Subscriber Credentials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No concealment of permanent identifiers No specific policies for GUTI reallocation 	[40], [53], [52], [49], [21], [3], [51]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Concealment of SUPI via SUCI GUTI reallocation after Registration and Service Request
Authentication Procedure	Lack of randomness and the use of XOR in AUTS	[56]	Enhanced randomness mechanisms
UP Confidentiality	Optional support	[21], [3]	UE and gNB mandatory support
UP Integrity	Optional support	[21], [4], [6]	UE and gNB mandatory support
UE Capabilities	No security transfer of UE capabilities	[44]	CP security before transfer of capabilities

TABLE 5. Overview of 5G Security Vulnerabilities and Enhancements

operator in NSA mode. This absence allows an adversary to perform data manipulation, identity mapping, and impersonation attacks (i.e., *MitM* attacks) even if confidentiality is active [4], [6], [21].

UE Radio Capabilities: Transmitting radio capabilities information before the CP security activation (*Security Mode Command* message) could lead to Identification, Binding Down, and Battery Drain attacks [44]. Given the obtained results, most of the deployments enclosed by Operator B in Spain and the ones from Operator B in the USA (see Table 3), are susceptible to these attacks.

The implementation of active data collection methodologies (e.g., [40], [57]) would enrich the obtained results, allowing an in-depth analysis of the security features not only from a network subscriber perspective but from the view of an active attacker willing to exploit the available vulnerabilities. However, delving into these practices not only violates legal standards but also breaches ethical boundaries, as they involve unauthorized access and potential infringement on privacy and security protocols.

E. Discussion and Recommendations

The analysis presented in this work highlights a gap between the security enhancements specified in the 3GPP standards for 5G and their actual implementation in the surveyed commercial networks across Europe and North America. This disparity stems from a confluence of technical, economic, and operational challenges faced by operators. A first factor is the phased migration from 4G to 5G infrastructure. While 5G SA deployments, particularly observed in North America (Section V.A), show progress towards adopting newer security features, the prevalence of NSA deployments [2] and inconsistencies even within SA rollouts indicate that the entire security potential of 5G is yet to be fully realized. This is presumably because operators may have prioritized rapid deployment and backward compatibility over full 5G security adoption, especially during transitional phases. This

approach, while economically pragmatic, delays critical security enhancements. Furthermore, a second factor is the optionality of certain mechanisms in 3GPP specifications (e.g., GUTI refresh policies), which allows operators to deprioritize their implementation due to computational overhead or interoperability concerns with legacy systems.

Among the identified vulnerabilities, three stand out as most critical as depicted in Table 6. Here we discuss them as well as provide the corresponding recommendations and best practices to mitigate them:

- **Cleartext Identifiers in NSA:** The lack of SUCI and the transmission of IMSI in NSA networks, and even in some failed SA registration attempts, remains a critical vulnerability, exposing users to tracking and impersonation attacks [40], [53] and directly contradicting 5G’s privacy promises. This situation directly impacts trust in the operator (especially among enterprise clients, governments and privacy-conscious customers given the failure to deliver the promised privacy guarantees or even lead to the violation of legal requirements in regions where the leakage of personally identifiable information is protected (e.g. GDPR in Europe). To address this issue is essential that operators prioritize the transition to 5G SA. In SA deployments, SUCI concealment (using Profile A or B) must be universally implemented, and *Null-scheme* usage should be strictly limited to exceptional, standardized cases (e.g., emergency services).
- **Predictable Temporary Identifiers:** The failure to implement all mandatory GUTI refresh triggers (especially after paging) and the use of predictable or time-correlated GUTI/TMSI values significantly undermine user anonymity and facilitate tracking [21], [51], [55]. The presence of user traceability demonstrates a complete lack of attention to security best practices from the operator, which could harm the customer’s confidence in its network. As with the previous vulnerability,

Category	Vulnerability	Recommendation / Best Practices
Clear text identifiers in 5G NSA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Permanent identifiers sent in clear text in NSA and failed SA registrations • Lack of SUCI implementation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prioritize transition to SA deployments • Enforce usage of SUCI using profiles A or B • Restrict the usage of Null Scheme to exceptional scenarios (e.g., emergency services)
Predictable temporary identifiers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Predictable or time-correlated GUTI/TMSI • Missing mandatory GUTI refresh triggers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Usage of pseudorandom number generators for temporary identifiers allocation to minimize predictability and time correlation • Strict adherence to 3GPP-defined GUTI refresh policies
Lack of UP integrity protection	UP data vulnerable to injection/hijacking even with confidentiality enabled	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mandatory UP integrity protection for both SA and NSA deployments

TABLE 6. 5G Network Security Vulnerabilities and Recommendations

it could also lead to legal consequences due to the violation of location privacy. To solve this, it is a good practice to strictly adhere to all 3GPP-defined GUTI refresh policies. Furthermore, operators should implement secure pseudo-random number generators for GUTI/TMSI allocation, eliminating predictability and time correlations.

- **Lack of UP Integrity:** Since UP integrity is left as optional by 3GPP, user data is vulnerable to manipulation even when confidentiality is enabled, facilitating attacks like data injection or session hijacking [4], [6], [21]. Opening the possibility to potential data manipulation will definitely damage the operator’s trust, especially in critical sectors such as autonomous driving or remote health, where network reliability is key to ensure public and health safety. The general recommendation to address this issue is to treat UP integrity protection as mandatory in all 5G deployments (both SA and NSA, leveraging Release 17 features for the latter).

Applying these actions requires a multi-stakeholder approach, aligning economic incentives with security imperatives. Regulatory bodies could incentivize SA adoption and reduce ambiguity whenever possible, while operators should transparently communicate security limitations during transitional phases. Vendors must ensure UE support for advanced algorithms (e.g., 256-bit keys) to enable future-proof security. Academia and industry collaborations can further refine monitoring tools to audit real-world compliance, as demonstrated in this work.

VI. Conclusions

5G networks are expected to significantly improve the security of mobile users, thanks to the newly introduced features that address identified 4G vulnerabilities. In this

paper, we analyzed the progress of some current 5G commercial network deployments in Europe and North America with respect to the expected implementation of security features defined by the 3GPP standards. In order to do so, we collected a dataset comprising 5G measurements from different operators in three European countries (Spain, France, and Germany), the United States of America, and Canada, covering both urban and suburban scenarios. The network operators considered in our study have a market share of 78% in Europe, 99% within the USA, and 30% of Canada. While our results only apply to the studied networks, due to economies of scale, our conclusions may be reasonably expected to refer to other European countries and countries/states in North America. Despite this, for a worldwide overview, similar analyses need to be carried out in other regions such as Asia, Africa, or South America.

Our results show that current 5G network deployments miss expectations on i) providing improved privacy and anonymity to subscriber identifiers (transmitting them in clear text), ii) refreshing often enough temporal subscriber identifiers and employing appropriate randomization techniques in the process (facilitating subscriber identification and tracking), iii) additional confidentiality protection (inheriting security vulnerabilities from previous generations) and iv) UE radio capabilities are sometimes transferred without protection (enabling bidding down and battery drain attacks). The datasets collected and used for this study will be made publicly available for research purposes upon publication.

As already reported in [10], we are in the midst of the 4G to 5G migration, expected to be mature by 2025. Thus, as we get closer to this date, we expect operators to increasingly deploy 5G security features accordingly, covering the gaps identified by our work.

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